

MAXIMIZING TEXT TO SPEAK ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT: EFL learners have difficulties in speaking English due to the lack of English oral inputs to motivate them to use English orally. English texts are considered as immediate available resources of input that can be maximized to help EFL learners to speak English. English text is very significant to be used as inputs for oral English since it offers rich linguistic inputs, as a model to contextually use English in communication process, to lower our anxiety since we can always look back to the text whenever we need, to help the learners feel confident in English speaking, and to provide information about how to use English properly. English texts can be used to practice conversation, to have a discussion, and to have an interview. To maximize the use of English texts, there are three stages that can be implemented: presentation, practice, and production. By maximizing English texts in classroom for practicing oral English, EFL learners can build their awareness in using English orally and can monitor their own mistakes when using English orally. Besides providing environment for EFL learners to practice their English skills, the continuous use of text in EFL classroom can also help students improving their motivation and developing their self confidence, as well as reducing their anxiety in using English. If these text-based speaking experiences become habit, EFL learners can build their awareness in using English and can monitor their own mistakes.

INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of learning a language is to use that language communicatively. Of all four language skills, speaking skill seems to be the immediate requirement for EFL learners to engage themselves in a conversation with other speakers of English (Zhang, 2009).

Logically speaking, as EFL learners, we need sufficient knowledge of English before we start to use English orally in communication process. However, compared with English native speakers and ESL acquirer, we have a very limited

access to oral inputs as resources of our English knowledge. That is because we do not have natural and immediate need to use English in our daily life, let alone to speak with native speakers in real life conversation. This condition has caused difficulties for learners to experience the use English (Zhang, 2009).

Consequently, the goal of learning English cannot be successfully achieved.

During my personal journey as both EFL learner as teacher of EFL, I have noticed that the classic problem found in the process of teaching and learning English is the lack of using English orally in the class. The situation is almost typical: students tend to keep their eyes widely open on their handout or textbooks but avoid answering the questions. Because teachers get no response from their students, they keep talking on and on throughout the lesson, either by using their first language or by using English. Class is then teacher-centered.

Regarding this problem, I consider that the basic problem of TEFL is the lack of resources which provide rich inputs to help us learn, acquire, and increase our knowledge of English in order to experience the use of English. Since we do not engage in real life communication context as oral resource, text should be regarded as available resource of inputs that we need. The purpose of this brief essay is then to discuss the exploration of text as linguistic inputs for us, EFL learners.

PRINCIPLES OF LEARNING TO USE ENGLISH COMMUNICATIVELY

The perspective of CC (Communicative Competence) is first claimed by Hymes in order to understand the use of language within the social and cultural

knowledge. This perspective suggests us to model the way native speakers use language to be engaged orally in real life communication context (Savignon, 2002; Bryam, 1997). Therefore, the activities of all language skills in classroom setting should be interrelated and continuously, as a simulation to the language activities in the real life communication. I hereby summarize eight CC principles as described by Savignon (2002) into three most dominant principles to be implemented in EFL classroom, as follows:

1. Language teaching should be based on a view of language as communication in real life context.
2. Learner's competence is relative, errors are tolerated and diversity is recognized and accepted as part of language learning development.
3. No single methodology is prescribed to teach how to use target language.

What has been suggested by these three principles to us is to freely experience the use of English. For that reason, we need as many inputs as possible to develop the desired awareness of using English, to convert the learned rules of target language into acquired rules (internalization). Related to this internalization, Krashen (2009) has postulated the inputs hypothesis under the principles of SLA/L (Second Language Acquisition/ Learning). The inputs hypothesis suggests us to move from our current competence and prior knowledge (i), to the next level of more advanced competence and knowledge ($i + 1$). This $i + 1$ hypothesis imply the available environment which is rich with linguistic inputs needed to facilitate this internalization process.

Based on CC and SLA/L principles, we need an environment to allow us experiencing the use of English as if in real life communication context, free to use the language without being afraid of making mistakes, and enable ourselves to develop linguistic awareness in developmental stages. The more we use English to communicate, the more we are aware of using English appropriately.

EXPLORING TEXT IN EFL CLASSROOM

1. Theoretical Underpinning of Maximizing to Use English

The inseparable relationship of language learning and language use has become the focus point of Experiential Learning Theory. Experiential Learning Theory states that students can develop the target language skills through a set of experiences on specific language task (Kolb, 1984). First coined by Kolb, this theory emphasizes the role of experiences in the learning process. Learning process is viewed as the process whereby knowledge is created and resulted through experiences. We experience learning from what have been offered by educational institutions, and from our reflection upon everyday and personal experience, outside the institutions. Experience enriches our perception toward life. It helps us to reconcile internal and external reality, especially the reality of using target language in everyday situation.

Experiential Learning Theory believes that students are best learning through experiences. During experiencing the learning process through sets of activities (such as simulations, role-plays, or dramas), students can perceive new information and then process or transform that new information, both in concrete

ways and in thinking abstractly by using logic and reason. In line with the spirit of communicative principles, this theory believes that when we learn to use English, we experience new situation of communication. Throughout our experiences, we can always learn something from it; whether it is learning from our mistakes which lead to misunderstanding, or learning the factors which leads to successful communication.

Experiential Learning Theory encourages students to analyze their learning experiences by reflecting, evaluating and reconstructing the experiences, to make it more useful and lead them to experience further learning stages (Moon, 1994). Experience is the foundation of learning development, and it is also used as a stimulus for learning. Through experiences, students can actively construct their own personal impression on English learning and English use. It means that we need an environment to allow us experiencing the use of English as if in real life communication context, free to use the language without being afraid of making mistakes, and enable ourselves to develop linguistic awareness in developmental stages. The more we use English to communicate, the more we are aware of using English appropriately.

Thus, text can be used to facilitate teachers creating environment needed for students. Students can maximize the use of all kinds of text during three stages of experiencing language learning and use; presentation, practice and production. At first, teachers should present an item of language being learned, in a context or situation which will clarifies the meaning of the language item itself. For example, by using descriptive text about Candi Borobudur or Candi Prambanan

which is already provided in the textbooks or handouts, teachers can introduce the expressions of explaining the historical points of tourism spots. This stage is called as presentation stage. During this stage, teachers can encourage students to find as many resources as possible related to the language item which is being learned.

At second stage, teachers assign students to practice what they have learned. The students should practice the language item itself through controlled exercises, sentences, or dialogs which are already provided by the resources. This stage is called as practice stage. In this stage, teachers should be available to monitor students' practice and to clarify language issues. All of these inputs will enrich their knowledge of using English. They can focus on the grammatical structure, the choice of diction, or the use of cohesive devices.

The third stage is production stage, in which the students should produce what they have learned and practiced through simulations, dramas, or role-plays. During this stage, they can produce their own dialogs based on what they have learned. To make their English production more interesting, they can record their performances and present the performances in video format, use PowerPoint to show the tourism spots that they want to explain, or create videoclips to promote the tourism spot.

Stimulated by language inputs which are provided by texts, videos, sounds and pictures as resources, student can use the language inputs in a given context or situation. The stimulus, then, may be filtered by several factors such as previous knowledge, previous experiences of learning and using English, emotions, self-

conception, choice of diction, and personal needs or wants to use English communicatively. Then, students interpret the stimulus that they have already obtained from the resources by relating it to their previous knowledge and experiences, and the given context.

This interpretation will be conveyed through students' behavioral responses, cognitive responses, and affective responses. Behavioral responses are expressed by students' attitude toward the language activities and the use of multimedia to facilitate their English experiences. Cognitive responses are showed by the ability of using English assisted by multimedia and implementing the knowledge of English, and affective responses are reflected by students' opinions and feelings toward the experiences, as reflected by their personal journals or annotations.

2. Significances of Using Text in Learning to Use English

I have discussed previously that the immediate resource for EFL learners is all reading texts in English textbooks and handouts, and the experiences of learning and using English are best conducted in three stages (presentation, practice, and production). Hence, the available text can be maximized into series of text-based speaking activities to facilitate students experiencing the use of English. There are several significances of text in EFL classroom, as also suggested by Zhang (2009), as follows:

- a. We can gain knowledge of using English appropriately from all kind of texts. Text provides rich example of linguistic inputs such as:

- 1) Grammatical structures: the use of tenses, active and passive voices, andif-conditional forms.
 - 2) Expressions: agreements and disagreements, opinions, or conclusions.
 - 3) Register and its definition; specific terms in agricultural, politics, or economics.
 - 4) Cohesive devices: listing, giving examples, generalizing, highlighting, or reformulation.
 - 5) Prepositional phrases.
 - 6) Phrasal verbs and linking verbs.
 - 7) Idioms.
 - 8) Punctuation marks and spelling.
- b. We can experience the use of English communicatively by using text more and more. All linguistic inputs, which are often studied separately in the class, are contextually used in the text. Accordingly, text can become a model for us to contextually use all linguistic inputs in the communication process (Zhang, 2009). Taking advantages of such inputs will enrich our knowledge of English.
- c. The availability of text as inputs can help us to be confident in using English, as well as to lower our anxiety since we can always look back to the text whenever we need.
- d. Whenever we make mistakes in using English, we can find information about our mistakes by finding help from text. This

information is really helpful to raise our awareness in using English appropriately. For example, how to use prepositions in the right position, how to split the infinitives, or how to use collocations.

SUGGESTIBLE ACTIVITIES OF MAXIMIZING TEXT AS RESOURCE OF LINGUISTIC INPUTS

In attempt to create a classroom environment for learners to experience the use of English communicatively, in this section I try to point out three simple text-based speaking activities for maximizing the use of text. The activities are described below:

1. Using text to have a conversation.

In this activity, I assign the students to have a conversation based on the text that they have read. Students can be grouped into two or three students. The plot and setting of their conversation can be a discussion between friends about the text currently read, a conversation between teacher and student, or a discussion between colleagues. I choose short story for beginner learners because it has a story plot and involves more than one character. For intermediate to advanced learners, I can use various kinds of texts such as narrative, descriptive, procedural, and academic reading text from TOEFL or IELTS reading section. All they have to do is to reconstruct the narrative structure of the text into a conversational structure. To do so, I ask the students to follow these steps:

- a. Choosing the characters based on the characters in the story; kind of animals (if it is fable), fictional people, or imaginary characters such as Peter Pan or Rapunzel.
 - b. Writing the conversation based on the plot written in the story. Students can pay attention on the direct and indirect speech marks in the text to decide the dialogs of their characters.
 - c. Controlling the flow of their conversation by using WH questions. Answering WH questions will help students to focus on the text being understood, for example:
 - 1) what is being written in the text and why,
 - 2) where does it take place,
 - 3) what are the stages of process being explained in the text (if it explains a procedure of something),
 - 4) when do the important events take place, how does it happen, who the people are and what are their characteristics (if it is a fiction), or,
 - 5) why is it funny (if it is a language play).
 - d. Determining the narrative order of conversation by paying attention on the chronological devices such as ‘once upon a time’, ‘at first’, ‘after that’, ‘suddenly’, or ‘in the end’.
2. Using text as inputs to have a discussion

During this activity, upper intermediate to advanced students can discuss the information that they have obtained from the text. I use for and against essay in this activity as this text is rich with personal opinions and

debatable sentences. Here are several examples of some expressions as linguistic features that are provided in the text:

- a. Giving opinion: ‘in my opinion’, ‘to me’, ‘from my point of view’.
 - b. Expressing agreement: ‘I definitely agree that’ ‘hence, I am confident that’, ‘there is no doubt that’.
 - c. Expressing disagreement: ‘I doubt that’, ‘I shall argue that’.
 - d. Summarizing: ‘to conclude’, ‘to sum up’.
 - e. Contrasting point: ‘however’, ‘in contrast’.
 - f. Giving example: ‘let’s take a look at’, ‘for instance’
3. Using text as inputs to interview

I consider this activity as suitable for all levels of learners. In this activity, I choose biography or autobiography of famous person as a resource. This activity is a pair-work role play, in which one student should play as a famous person being interviewed and the other student should be the interviewer. The one who acts as an interviewer can use WH questions to help preparing the script for the role, and the other who acts as the person being interviewed can be focusing on:

- a. The use of proper noun such as name of certain places, people, specific events or occasions, or name of buildings.
- b. Set of adjective words to describe physical appearances, characteristics, descriptions of places and buildings,

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improving their motivation and developing their self confidence,as well as reducing their anxiety in using English. If these text-based speaking experiences become habit, EFL learners can build their awareness in using English and can monitor their own mistakes.

CONCLUSION

It is very important for all of us, EFL learners, to have sufficient linguistic inputs, to empower our communication in English. The use of text, as the most immediate resource, should be maximized to help ourselves taking advantages of all linguistic inputs already provided. Experiences in using English will help us to develop awareness of using English that we need, and familiarize ourselves to use English orally. Furthermore I hope that this brief essay can be counted as preliminary essay into deeply investigating the effect of using explicit instructions in text-based activities in EFL classroom to improve EFL learners' language skills.

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